

Editorial

Novel Materials and Processes for Photovoltaic Technology

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Abstract

The human being can benefit of the Photovoltaics (PVs) advantages, such as high reliability in devices, low operating costs, quick installation, no emissions, no combustion, etc. In the last decades the third generation PV technologies have changed the paradigm and attracted the attention of research community, experts, entrepreneurs and funding agencies all over the world. In the special issue “Novel Materials and Processes for Photovoltaic Technology”, the most renewed emerging technologies have been investigated in relation with some open issues, such as applications, efficiency, stability, cost and sustainability.

Keywords

Photovoltaics; dye-sensitized solar cells; perovskite solar cells; solar energy

1. Introduction

Photovoltaic (PV) technology is the symbol of a sustainable future in many countries around the globe [1]. As a result, numerous investments have been made in research, development, demonstrators, and production lines. No other renewable technology has received such a strong appreciation from the public, politics and industry. New technologies have traced the way for new materials, products, and additional market segments [2,3]. Engineering, nanoscience, nanotechnology, and surface science have contributed to introducing new materials and customized processes for solar. In the last decades, many research institutes, companies, and consortia have demonstrated that the new concept of solar cell technology can achieve high performance, large application areas, and industrialization. There are different types of solar devices among the third generation PVs that have recently emerged [3,4], and their benefits and issues have been exhibited: dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC) [5,6], hybrid and organic solar cells [7], quantum dot solar cells [8], and perovskite (PVSK) solar cells (PSC) [9,10].

Here, I show the successful invited submissions to the Special Issue of *Energies* on the subject area of “Novel Materials and Processes for Photovoltaic Technology”. The third generation PV technologies chosen by the authors are DSSC and PSC.

2. Special Issue Articles

In the special issue, DSSC (the first developed) and PSC were the third generation PV technologies mainly investigated.

The following features make DSSC technology suitable for building-integrated PVs (BIPVs) [11], consumer electronics, indoor applications [12]: different device colors [13], transparency in the visible range [14], low correlation with the light angle [15,16], better operation in diffuse light compared to traditional PV technologies [17], bifacial concept [18], low cost fabrication processes [11], possibility to use rigid and flexible substrates [19], and environmental sustainability.

The comparable fabrication procedures with organic electronics and DSSC have boosted the success of PSC technology [20,21]. Moreover, the organometal halide perovskites unique physical-chemical properties [22–24] (high absorption coefficient, ambipolar charge transport, large charge carriers lifetime and diffusion length, flexible bandgap tuning, low exciton binding energy) permitted to develop a solution process PV technology with power conversion efficiencies (25.7% for the single junction) higher than any thin film PV and closely resembling the one of silicon [25].

In the special issue, semi-transparent dye-sensitized solar modules (DSSMs) and panels (DSSPs) have been fabricated to filter the sunlight from the roof of an Aquaponic greenhouse [26] according to recent progress [27]. The Agrovoltaic hot topic is related to the optimization of land by combining solar PV and food crops [28]. Greenhouses are equipped with many control devices for temperature, lighting, fans and monitoring. DSSC can both satisfy the energy needs and selective control the light entering [29,30]. In the published paper, the aperture area (312.9 cm²) module efficiency and AVT (average visible transmittance) are equal

to 3.88% and 35%, respectively [26]. The devices exhibited thermal and light stability during accelerated tests and were laminated to realize 10 panels (2 m²). The produced power was about 3 W in compliance with energy needs in a greenhouse. Moreover, the plant growing was not affected by DSSPs light filtering. In a PSC the electron transporting layer (ETL) and the hole transporting layer (HTL) are mandatory to drain from the photoactive layer both electrons and holes to the respective electrodes and to limit the recombination [31]. The hole transporting material (HTM) is responsible for stability, efficiency and cost of a PSC. Since the HTM doping agents are mainly hygroscopic, the research is focused to find dopant-free HTM such as small molecules or polymers.

The first review article in the special issue collects all the relevant organic dopant-free small-molecule HTMs adopted to fabricate PSCs with efficiency above 15% [32]. The HTMs are classified according to their topology (1D linear, 2D star-shaped, 3D spiro-like) and related features. HTMs based on benzodithienosilole, benzodipyrrole, dithienopyrrole, bithiophencarboximide, truxenes, spirobifluorene and spiro[fluorene-9,9'-xanthene] cores guaranteed PSCs with efficiency more than 20%. About the molecules compaction, the authors reported how the hole mobility can be improved by reducing the contact distance between packed molecules, in particular if the lowest distances include the chemical centers (simply oxidized and reduced). Moreover, the molecular planarity can help to improve the cell efficiency thanks to the stacking and the high contact of molecules. The review showed also high stability compounds for potential commercialization.

In the special issue, one article experimented an alternative efficient and stable low-cost fluorene-xanthene-based HTM [33]. The reference Spiro-OMeTAD HTM has high efficiency but it is expensive and has low stability in presence of humidity. The authors reported, for the first time on large area cell, the low cost X55 HTM with a deeper HOMO level and higher hole mobility and conductivity with respect to Spiro-OMeTAD HTM [34]. The PSCs based on the homogeneous X55 film show higher V_{oc} and maximum power point stabilized efficiency with respect to the reference HTM, because of poor defects and pin holes. The efficiency loss was about 15% lower with respect to Spiro-OMeTAD at 1000 h ISOS-D-1 test (room temperature at 50% humidity).

The last review article is focused on n-i-p PSC efficiency and stability improvement by interfacial engineering through passivation treatment to reduce non-radiative recombination [35]. The passivation acts as a shielding layer to protect the PVSK surface by reducing the trap states at the grains and the grains boundaries. The paper introduces the surface reconstruction concept, i.e. the formation of a 3D [36], low-D interlayer [37] and the surface reconstruction with mixed-salt through synergistic effect [38]. The first two approaches reconstruct the PVSK surface through the formation of an optimized layer of 3D or low-D PVSK. Moreover, the low-D PVSK can enhance the surface hydrophobicity. The mixed salts approach combines different improvements. In the last years, some passivation approaches have been upscaled to module level [39,40].

The authors found how there is a lack of studies about the material selection criteria and passivation mechanisms understanding.

3. Conclusions

The special issue “Novel Materials and Processes for Photovoltaic Technology” is composed by four papers, two research and two review articles. These cover some hot topics related to DSSC and PSC as large area alternative application, efficiency, stability, cost and sustainability. In this editorial article the guest editor has briefly summarized the main finding and consideration from the published invited submissions. The guest editor would like to thank the outstanding contributors, reviewers, *MDPI Energies* publisher and editorial staff.

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